

ISic1263

I.Sicily inscription 1263

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140752

1. Θ (εοῖς) [Κ(αταχθονίοις)].

2. [Ρ]ῶσκις Τρόφ [ιμος]

3. ἔζησεν ἔτη [— —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492870

EDCS 39101632

PHI 140752

Bibliography

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